

TECHNOLOGICAL MODES OF MONITORING THE LOCATION OF MINES IN THE MINE AND THE SLOPE BORDER OF THE BLAST AREA

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Abstract: A remote real-time monitoring system has been developed for real-time remote monitoring in mining enterprises. We can technologically monitor general processes of mine slope deformation and internal forces. The system is based on cloud computing technology and 5S multimedia flow monitoring data transmission system. Now we use it for process control, in the Tebin Bulak open-pit iron mine of the Republic of Karakalpakstan to monitor the horizontal displacement of potential sliding surfaces. Compared with traditional geodetic methods of geometric monitoring, the results show that this monitoring system has high accuracy (0.01 mm) and real-time monitoring for 24 hours. These features can make early warnings of mine slopes from many dimensions, and to ensure the safe, continuous and efficient production of mines. It is also possible to provide some reference and useful for the prevention and control of mine slope disasters through the application of information-based early warning technology.

Key words: Angle of coordinates of location of open mine; slope monitoring; cloud computing; 5S transmission system; real-time monitoring system, error mode in technological control,

Introduction

Landslides are a common disaster in open-pit mining. There are many of them. Mine slope monitoring methods around the world. For example, surface deformation monitoring, underground well inclinometer and voltage monitoring, acoustic emission and microseismic monitoring, groundwater monitoring, and meteorological parameters monitoring. Geometric monitoring of slope deformation is one of the most common methods. I Otelbayev Azizbek, based on my many researches and experiences, I witnessed the distortion of the slope angles of the mine, mainly when the distance of the slope angles in the mine expands by the same value. This has a negative impact on the

economy of the mine. Although there are geometric monitoring methods in traditional geodetic surveying with high accuracy, they require heavy workloads and high costs, and it is difficult arrangement of points and sparse measurement points. Under large-scale and complex ground conditions, voltage measurement is very limited. It's hard to get sufficiently important displacement data for a large-scale open pit mine. This will do it is not possible to provide complete and accurate information for the prevention of accidents on mining slopes. With the development of the Internet and electronic information and communication technologies, slope monitoring and warning systems have developed to a certain extent. This tech tracking equipment has moved from desktop software to mobile app and cloud platform. Monitor and warn computer desktop software to set data and loading and warning value and display the output designed and applied in highway, mine, railway and slope area. They have successfully developed signal receiving cloud platforms, mobile applications for avalanche and highway monitoring and warning systems, and remote control technology on the side.

Slope safety monitoring technology

Extremely steep during construction and use information monitoring on rock slope, stability necessary. The principles of the explosion safety monitor are as follows (1) Turn on the security monitor blasting vibration should be present throughout the construction period and feedback analysis should be timely. (2) data assembled from dynamic and static monitor, switch and public monitor must be inside public and local monitor

Picture 1. Flat blast optimization dimensions.

Placement of various resistance bands terms of two free faces. stable, high precision and simple rapid instruments and methods is the previous choice. Many methods and devices must be adopted to observe the same variable for the main part and the results should be cross-checked. (4) sites and monitoring times must meet blasting safety requirements to guarantee the fulfillment of

achievement data and reliable. (5) there must be other external factors such as building environment or weather conditions is taken into account. Different projects need different monitor tools. Velocimeter, accelerometer and dynamic voltage the gauge is used to obtain the movement and dynamic parameters of the rocks. The highest level of particle vibration speed the main controllable parameter that reflects about the dynamic response after blasting. Similarly, the drill is inclinometer and multipoint extensometer used to monitor the displacement change. integration of The collected data can be analyzed in steady state and slip trend. As for the stress monitor, he uses it often pressure cell, anchor dynamometer, etc. However, most of this equipment can only monitor one item and cannot perform real-time continuous monitoring. The slope of the mine is unstable characteristics of suddenness and uncertainty. Therefore, it is very necessary to carry it perform high-precision, large-scale and 24-hour real-time monitoring for mine slope. In order to achieve high-precision, large-scale and continuous real-time monitoring of mine slopes in complex terrain conditions and cloud computing technology has been introduced in the mine slope monitoring. In conjunction with 5S data transfer, the system applies to those concerned displacement monitoring projects of potential sliding surfaces. In addition, cloud computing technology can store and efficiently analyze large amounts of data and give early warning. It also solves the problems of traditional monitoring methods It requires a lot of manpower, the tracking accuracy is low, and it cannot perform continuously monitor. Compared to other methods of slope monitoring systems, remote real-time the monitoring system has the following advantages: (1) data collection module and data transmission module integrated into the data acquisition and transmission module, and considering the waterproof and insect-proof functions of the module, power supply unit and PC can be directly connected to the debug serial port easy-to-use data collection and transfer module. (2) There is a high measurement accuracy of about 0.01mm. This can lead to disaster more accurate slope prediction to avoid excessive mine deformation there is technical support supervision for the prevention and control of slope and mine slope disasters. Our goal is that we will be able to prove that the slope angle can be accurately estimated in the order of 0.001-0.50.

Scheme of system composition and technology

The remote real-time monitoring system uses cloud computing and 5S data transmission to complete automated monitoring, data collection and early warning. Monitoring the system is based on a cloud platform that can collect and

store large amounts of data real time. The system consists of five parts, namely sensors, data acquisition modules, As shown in Picture 2, we can learn more information about the system by studying the data transfer modules, cloud platforms, and user terminals.

Picture 2. (1) The interface of the sensor device is flexible and can be connected to switching, strain and force measuring devices. It can be continuous or real-time continuous collection of various monitoring objects of mine slopes. (2) The data acquisition module monitors and reads the operation of the entire system stores the sensor data and acts as a signal transmission wave.

(3) The data transmission module is based on the 5S transmission system and overcomes disadvantages of traditional data transmission relying on a single GSM network. It's not affected by network signal sources and can transmit data in real time.

(4) The user terminal can be installed on personal computers and mobile phones. The system may allow it admin permissions to different people that make it easy to view and change data and allows defining parameters at any time.

Results

(1) This system realizes the organic integration of cloud computing platform and 5S technology. It relies on a cloud computing processing platform to achieve massive scale data storage. It uses 5S technology to perform real-time data transmission and data processing and making early warning decisions.

(2) The system has rich interfaces, wide range and high precision. It adopts high-precision and wide-range traction cable replacement sensor, which can record more number. data and a high measurement accuracy of 0.01 mm.

(3) The system has a diversified power supply system. Can be powered by solar energy, battery power, 220 V DC power and power supply mode are automatically changed.

(4) Data monitoring is convenient and fast. Through computer, mobile phone and other terminal communication, users can monitor, control and query data measure points in real time anytime and anywhere.

Early warning information is possible can be sent to multiple people's mobile phones for seamless real-time monitoring monitoring data by the key person responsible for the project. the surface of the slope consists mainly of rock groups of the Quaternary period.

Conclusions

With the construction of many hydroelectric plants Open pit, unprecedented challenges blast excavation and control the stability of extremely high steep rocks. the slope is constantly updated. The main work and conclusions of this article are summarized as follows:

(1) A number of design principles and stability criteria of extreme mountain slopes are summarized. up. Stability analysis is mainly static and dynamic analysis. The open pit combined with the safety factor of the static criterion and the dominant oscillation frequency of the dynamic criterion is two. The most commonly used index in practice.

(2) Blast excavation processes are generally digging from top to bottom and wise layer and zone division. Proper arrangement, It is possible to strengthen before digging, such as strengthening and digging at the same time reduce the negative impact of the explosion. It is also possible to select either lateral hollow face pre-slicing or optimized smooth blasting reducing and controlling damage to stock rock explosion vibration. And high in situ stress Open pits should not be neglected. A combination of pre-separation and smooth blasting or process optimization can be used controlling the effects of in-situ stress on some level.

(3) Conventional reinforcement measures, e.g bolt, anchor, anti-slide pile, can only solve part of it stability issues. When it comes to complex geological conditions, new technology, etc anchor cave, shear-resistance tunnel, may be a better choice for large-scale slope engineering. Explosive damage and loose bursts are easy occurs in the near field of the explosion source, and in the far field, an explosion vibration is formed. In practice, optimization of blasting parameters, focus on accuracy of scale dimensions.

The system can monitor multi-source parameters of the slope group, e.g single-point displacement, two-point relative displacement, anchor bolt tension, concrete voltage, precipitation, temperature and humidity, slope and groundwater level and possible automatic early warning of potential slope disasters via SMS and email. The study of slope monitoring and early warning

cases took more than two years and Remote slope monitoring and early warning confirmed the effectiveness of the cloud platform and appendix, revealing the law of change of slope horizontal displacement and compared with total station measurement results. It proved the reliability of remote monitoring and early warning system. In summary, remote slope monitoring compares favorably with other monitoring methods and a cloud computing-based warning system can track high-level potential landslides accuracy, saving human resources and real-time 24-hour monitoring.

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